

Indian Cinema: A Feminist Discourse

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There has been a very strong impact of Hindi cinema on society through the ages. There have been changes in the institutions of marriage, and instances of live-in relationships have come of age; there has been a constant and continuous shift from joint families to nuclear families. Elaborating on the changes in the cultural practices, preferences have changed about food habits, clothing, choice of career options, and belief systems. The distinctive contribution of the present paper is to offer an understanding of the impact of movies on Indian culture, especially on the youth, by extracting information from the structured and in-depth interviews.

Representations through different media formats have always proved to be catalysts for social change due to their immense potential in influencing and shaping the attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of the masses. The media has played a significant role in bringing to the fore the existing reality of women's status and their changing paradigms. It is a well-argued fact that issues such as inequality, considering them inferior and incapable, especially in relation to their male counterparts, were and are still an impediment to their progression as individuals in different sections of society.

Women's empowerment in its myriad manifestations has been dealt with by the different forms of media, such as Broadcasting media, print media, social media, digital media, the internet, etc., wherein Cinema enjoys the status of the most widely accessible medium in almost all the different types of media. This paper attempts to study the representation of women in Indian Films so as to understand their role in shaping new perspectives on gender equality and also sensitizing people towards the reality associated with the issues. In films dealing with feminist issues, a very well framed questions are being posed related to their role in filmic narration, placement in the entire narrative in comparison to other prominent characters, etc

On closer introspection, we get to know the impact of films, as there are films that have dared to go beyond the conventional portrayal and created a new identity of the empowered woman. However, despite being key players in the development of the nation, some films do not treat Women at par with their male counterparts, and their role is a marginalized one in some of the films. To illustrate the multifaceted images in Indian Hindi films, Examples have been drawn from earlier films like Fire, Mother India, and the recent

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ones like Pink, Gulaab Gang, Kahaani, etc. Such films have proved to be a major milestone in setting up new trends in showcasing issues relevant to women and have come across as eye-openers for the masses, and therefore are an intriguing area of study.

Films, being indispensable cultural tools of social change, hold an important place in the social milieu in bringing change in the mindset of the people regarding established practices and values. The fight for equality and more prominently human rights has been taken up by several filmmakers so as to bring the issue to the limelight and also to enlighten the masses in exposing the actual story of women being involved. As said, the representation of women in cinema has been a major issue of debate amongst feminist film theorists in India. The complex and fascinating relationship between women and cinema has a substantial literature and some interesting work on Third World feminism, which illuminates aspects of the representation of women in Indian films. The representation of women and the representation by women on screen are essential for understanding the interplay between women and cinema in India (Gokulsing and Dissanayake, 1998).

Films are cultural signifiers and hence wield an enormous power to deeply influence our perceptions, our sensibilities, with specific reference to the culture and the society we are living in. Moreover, Cinema influences an individual's behaviour, perception, and position in their culture and society, and hence encompasses all the multifaceted aspects integral to society. The issue of the projection of women also occupies a unique place in cinema (Shekhawat, 2009). As a medium with the strongest influence on the Indian psyche, we explore through these portrayals how cinema has played an important role in promoting a new empowered identity of Indian women through recent shifts in its content of production. Laura Mulvey says that, "Men act, women appear. Men look at women; women watch themselves being looked at.". This quote suggests the position of women in the realm of the 'look'. In Indian cinema, women have been relegated to the passive position in film after film, as "bearer, not the maker of meaning", merely an appendage to the man, the wielder of power. (Mulvey, 1998, p. 384)

Initially, women were portrayed as timid, docile, and vulnerable in Indian cinema. A woman was usually considered a homemaker surviving under the protective shield of her husband. However, strong female roles have their main reliance on the vamps in the films, though the present delineation has undergone a rapid change. In the past, the cinema was mostly dominated by males on the celluloid due to their significant presence in the entire filmmaking arena, and as usual, off the celluloid due to the societal norms. Presently, women can be seen in multifaceted roles and share a position of parity in the changing scenario of Indian

cinema. A complete shift can be observed in the delineation of women's portrayal through films, and the female characters are more balanced, decisive, and powerful.

There have been revolutionary films like *Duniya Na Maane*, *Chetna*, etc but *Mother India* is a quintessential film that has gained the stature of a legend in Indian Cinema. Remarkable in its representation of showcasing the highly dignified image without succumbing to the clutches of poverty is a noteworthy aspect. This film has set a tone for the future generation of filmmakers to project women in a lead role, having all the essential attributes hitherto considered integral to their male counterparts.

Aandhi is one such film that incorporates the same ideological concept in its theme and treatment. *Bhumika* is yet another filmic mode to establish the irresistible desire of a female to lead a life on her own terms. The character is bold enough not to remain confined to the space allotted by her husband, but in her quest for love, happiness, and self-identity, keeps on shunting between so many males in her life and faces the challenges boldly. In a society where relationships are measured from the point of view of men, when a woman decides to mould the norm, she ends up being lonely. Trying to figure out who she is and what she is, his protagonist Usha finds herself trapped in unequal relationships, only to be told towards the end, 'beds change, men don't'. It rings a bell more than three decades after "*Bhumika*" hit the theatres. (The Hindu, 2014)

The same self-sufficient image of a woman gets highlighted in the film *Arth*, where actress Shabana Azmi has played the role of a self-sufficient woman ready to embark on a journey without any help. Despite her husband's extramarital affair and his decision to leave her, she dares to move forward in life. Another film, *Fire* from the trilogy of Deepa Mehta, shatters the stereotypes about women and questions the patriarchal mindset that seeks to control even the sexuality of women. With powerful dialogues and subtleties that an observant viewer is expected to catch on, the movie succeeds in having a profound effect on the viewers' minds.

Many critics argue that the movie only tackles one facet of oppression, that concerning sexuality. Noted Indian feminist authors Mary E. John and Tejaswini Niranjana wrote in 1999 that *Fire* reduces patriarchy to the denial and control of female sexuality. "Control of female sexuality is surely one of the ideological planks on which patriarchy rests. But by taking this idea literally, the film imprisons itself in the very ideology it seeks to fight ... 'Fire' ends up arguing that the successful assertion of sexual choice is indeed, the sole criterion for the emancipation of women."

Emergence of strong women characters has been a distinguishing characteristic of the last two decades in both the mainstream as well as offbeat, ranging from *Mirch Masala*, *Mandi*, *Sardari Begum*, and *Mrityudand* to *Lajja*, *Astitva*, *Chandni Bar*, *Pinjar*, *Chameli*, *Satta*, *Dor* and many others. Despite the fact that they were not highly popular, they managed to creep into the well-defined coterie of a patriarchal setup. There have been many upheavals in the entire journey of female-oriented films wherein the action era heroines have not been depicted as very strong and rational, and heroes were more powerful. Moreover, they were just represented as being shy, meek, dancing around the trees, without any important role in the film, but even in that scenario, one film *Mirch Masala* directed by Ketan Mehta in 1989, hit the theatres with a powerful message and became a trendsetter in showing the collective struggle of women as an entity.

With the recent changes in the filmmaking scenario, there have been films wherein women have been designated roles not just as sex symbols and side characters but as the main lead responsible to move the story forward. Hence, it can be observed that a woman is not just in the process of empowerment on the screen in her roles, but has also occupied a prominent place as a director and producer as well. The film “*Pink*” is a recently released powerful and brave Hindi mainstream film which focuses on young women who, in the course of their everyday struggle has to face innumerable issues related to their survival and instead of avoiding. They themselves come up with the solutions to deal with such issues in a bold and realistic way. This tendency of the present generation not to avoid but to come to terms with the problem is an area worth appreciating for women across the world.

It can be said that it has taken a long time for Bollywood filmmakers to communicate such a bold message through realistic characters and projection, which hint towards the prevailing status quo in the society and the country we live in, and the social mores that its women have had to abide by as a part of the prevalent patriarchy. Another film, “*Parched*” is quite acclaimed because of its realistic depictions and gives a ray of hope for the coming change. The spirit of the film is celebrating fights against an unjust system and society and emerging winners, not because they have well-intentioned men rescuing them, but because they can save themselves. *Parched* is a women-centric film and revolves around three ordinary women from rural areas of Rajasthan, where women are still considered the weaker sex. It not only showcases the trials and tribulations that rural women have to face in those places, but also highlights how men perceive their women.

A similar film, “*Gulaab Gang*” has also helped demystify and elucidate the stark reality of the struggle that backward class women have to face in Indian villages and towns even today, through its projections of strong women who stand up for themselves and refuse to take any wrong at the hands of the patriarchal

society. To highlight the fierce shade in women, the film “Mardaani” by Rani Mukherjee is an apt example in which her role is actually very challenging and, with aplomb, handles cases of child trafficking. An amalgamation of beauty and brains, she acts as a source of motivation. The perfect mix of strength and respect, her character acts as an inspiration for the entire women's community.

Another noteworthy performance by Rani Mukherjee is as Meera Gaity, an aggressive Journalist in the film “No One Killed Jessica” whose honesty towards her profession is exemplary and whose irresistible urge to fight against injustice enables a victim to get justice. She not only single-handedly reopened the case but also got the public involved and finally gave the much-needed closure to the family of the innocent girl who was murdered. Gaity is the perfect example of a modern, empowered woman who can bring about a larger change.

The portrayal of the boxer Mary Kom by Priyanka Chopra is yet another influential female role in the history of Indian cinema. The entire story of this world champion stands as a testimony for everyone who wants to dream and convert their dream into reality. In India, such films act as a perfect motivational symbol, where taking up sports as a career for women is considered not a very favourable sign. The exemplary success of the film serves as a great inspiration and motivation for all women who, due to their social conditioning, think their career would take a setback when they get married or embrace motherhood.

To conclude, it can be sad that the media, films, and other means of public communication have always had a great and powerful impact on the issues in the minds of the people. There have been numerous instances where various movies have faced several degrees of protests by various fundamentalist groups, with the idea that movies have a direct attack on Indian culture, destroying the cultural ethos of India, or at certain points, portray Indian culture in a poor light. However, there is another angle to it where it is politically motivated as well. In order to ensure political sustainability and survival, the political vendetta creates ruckus at times. Cinema is observed as a powerful medium of information, education, and entertainment results in the process of opinion building in various social groups. The impact of films is damaging to society and morality. Considering the deep impact and impression Bollywood movies create in the minds of the young generation, the need of the hour is to have a proper policy to safeguard the same and ensure the kind of movies screened do not have any content that can have a far-reaching negative impact on the nascent minds.

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